

Managing Editor's Column

Dear Readers,

welcome to the third issue of volume four. I want to thank all authors for their contributions and the editorial board for their review effort. I hope you will enjoy the papers.

This issue contains 7 articles: P. A. Carlson: Advanced Educational Technologies - Promise and Puzzlement; E. Aïmeur: Application and Assessment of Cognitive-Dissonance Theory in the Learning Process; K. Buckner, M. Gillham: A Comparative Evaluation of Print and Electronic Reviews of Multimedia Information Products; V. Makrakis, S. Retalis, A. Koutoumanos, N. Papaspyrou, M. Skordalakis: Evaluating the Effectiveness of an ODL Hypermedia System and Courseware at the National Technical University of Athens: A Case Study; S. McGee, B. Howard: Evaluating Educational Multimedia in the Context of Use; H. Ruokamo, S. Pohjolainen: Pedagogical Principles for Evaluation of Hypermedia-Based Learning Environments in Mathematics; C. W. Thackaberry, R. Rada: Estimation Metrics for Courseware Maintenance Effort

Yours sincerely,

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